

PROSPECTS OF USING THE OPPORTUNITIES OF THE STOCK MARKET IN INCREASING THE FLOW OF CAPITAL TO UZBEKISTAN

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Accelerating capital flow to the country through the stock market professional participants of the securities market, namely brokers, dealers, investment advisers, investment companies, investment funds, management companies, depositories, settlement clearing houses, registrars of securities owners, securities along with nominal depositors, the Republican Stock Exchange and other investment institutions are implemented using the infrastructure of the securities market. It is necessary to increase the size of the capital market in Uzbekistan through international financial resources and to integrate it into the infrastructure of the world stock market, as well as to raise the weight of the stock market infrastructure in the accumulation of domestic financial resources.

In cooperation with international organizations and financial institutions, efforts are being made to attract foreign investments to securities of Uzbek issuers in the world market. In particular, we can take as an example the sovereign Eurobonds (Eurobonds) of the Republic of Uzbekistan, whose trading was organized on the London Stock Exchange on February 14, 2019. After that, the resident commercial banks of Uzbekistan, as issuers, started the practice of placing Eurobonds on the international market. Of course, it is necessary for the government of the developing country, which is considered new for the world financial market, to place its instruments on the financial market and to open the way to the world market for its economic entities in the future. Of course, this practice was implemented by other countries before Uzbekistan. We will return to this topic below.

First of all, let's talk briefly about Eurobonds, "the first Eurobond was issued by the Italian company "Avtostrada" in 1963." Eurobonds are debt securities that can be sold in several markets at the same time, sold in foreign currency and on foreign markets. Eurobonds are securities denominated in US dollars with maturities ranging from 1 to 40 years.

So, what are the characteristics of sovereign Eurobonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan? Uzbekistan 1 bln. Placed US dollar Eurobonds in 2 different terms and in 2 tranches, i.e. 5-year and 10-year periods of 500 million US dollars with

the condition of paying 4.75% and 5.375% annual income (coupon), respectively. Initially, it was proposed to sell Eurobonds at a higher interest rate, i.e. 5-year bonds in the range of 5.625%-5.75% and 10-year bonds with a 6% yield, but on the day of the sale, 1 bln. 8.5 billion to the US dollar offer. Falling US dollar applications (demand) allowed bond yields (promised coupon percentage) to drop, and even at a reduced coupon rate, there were enough investors to satisfy the yield and trades were successful. Well, what is causing this is primarily the relationship between Uzbekistan's external debt and GDP (debt management strategy) and the positive assessment of the reforms being implemented in the country. Therefore, the "benchmark" of Uzbekistan's new fund instrument Eurobonds (determining the position and influence of the fund instrument in the international market in the future) was successfully implemented.

What were the goals of Uzbekistan behind the issuance of these sovereign Eurobonds? In our opinion, the main purpose of these Eurobonds was to introduce Uzbekistan's securities to the world market and to assess the attractiveness of Uzbekistan in the world in attracting capital. In fact, such large-scale debt relations made it necessary for the country to meet its needs for financial resources as the first priority. As a clear proof of our opinion, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4258 "On the effective use of funds from the placement of the first sovereign international bonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted only on April 2, 2019, and "889.2 mln. US dollars for deposits in commercial banks in our Republic, 20 mln. USD 89.9 million as a subordinated loan to Agrobank ATB. The US dollar was placed as a budget loan to the Navoi mining and metallurgical combine. The adoption of the decision on the placement of the loan only after a month and a half will undoubtedly increase the value of the borrowed funds. From this it seems that the strategy of using it in obtaining the loan was not predetermined and thus led us to draw the above conclusion.

We know that the movement (trading) of securities in the secondary market is positive, which is a very important feature in ensuring that the price of securities does not fall in the future and the liquidity of new instruments of the issuers of these securities in the market in the future. This is especially important for a country like Uzbekistan, which made its debut on the world stock market.

After this first practice of Uzbekistan in the world market, the debut of Uzsanoatkurilishbank ATB among our national companies in 2019 can be cited as an example.

On November 25, 2019, Uzsanoatkurilishbank ATB launched a 5-year 300 mln. issued international bonds in the amount of dollars. "The initial yield rate for bonds is set at 6.50%. The final coupon rate was 5.75% due to high demand. In relation to bonds, the volume of orders by investors is 1.2 billion. dollar, or 4 times more than the volume of the issue. As it can be seen from such a demand, the bonds of the first company of Uzbekistan were warmly welcomed by the international market. The attractiveness of securities in the market is expressed not only in the primary but also in the secondary market. The circulation of the first corporate Eurobonds of Uzbekistan on the secondary market not only shows its attractiveness, but also serves as a "market benchmark" for our national companies that are planning to introduce their international securities into circulation in our country in the future.

In addition, the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan stated in an interview with "Reuters" on February 14, 2019 that "Uzbekistan wants to buy U.S. Treasury bonds (U.S. Treasuries) by reducing the share of gold in the gold currency reserve." The chairman of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan also confirmed this opinion in an interview with the Bloomberg agency on July 11, 2019. However, on September 15, 2019, the Deputy Minister of Finance stated in an interview on his website "kun.uz" that Uzbekistan is not planning to buy US treasury bonds. In our opinion, this practice would not be justified at this time. Because, while Uzbekistan sells Eurobonds on the international market with a promise of 4.7 and 5.3% coupons, it does not make much sense for US Treasury bonds to buy bonds with a coupon yield of 1.47-2.79% (in 2019), even this even though the instrument is considered the most risk-free asset in the world. In addition, even if assets are diversified to reduce the amount of gold in the reserve, it is appropriate to allocate capital to assets with a higher rate of return (at least the rate of return that Uzbekistan promises to the world market).

we can conclude that the negative results recorded against the background of the current pandemic show that it is somewhat difficult to hope that the participation of our corporate structures as issuers in the world financial market will give positive results. Because we are witnessing an increase in the level of profitability promised in the international financial market, and a sharp drop in

market prices, which in itself is a proof that no one can guarantee that the bonds of our national companies will not be negatively affected.

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country, we can give a positive assessment of the fact that they entered into relations with Eurobonds in order to determine their place in the international market environment. Implementation of such practices in the future, taking into account the global situation, will create the basis for achieving more successful results in the future.

References:

1. Thomas Chemmanur, Gang Hu, Jiekun Huang. The Role of Institutional Investors in Initial Public Offerings. // The Review of Financial Studies, November 2010. - P.46.
2. Ufuk Gübilmez, Tomas 6 Briain. Bidding styles of institutional investors in IPO auctions. // Journal of Financial Markets, 2 June 2020, 100579. — P.21.
3. Chui Zi Ong, Rasidah Mohd-Rashid, Kamarun Nisham Taufil-Mohd. Do institutional investors drive the IPO valuation? // Borsa Istanbul Review, 19 May 2020.